

RECOVER-N3C Query # 1: Differences in acute visit characteristics in patients that will develop PASC

Do we see differences in the acute-phase for patients that will develop PASC?

Overall study inclusion criteria. Patients in the N3C database with a COVID-19 index date defined by the earlier of: a positive rt-PCR or antigen SARS-CoV-2 lab test result or a COVID-19 diagnosis (U07.1). Patients that died within 45 days of COVID-19 index date were excluded because they are indeterminate with respect to PASC. All analyses are applied to data in N3C from the v61 N3C data release from January 27, 2022. Patients from 62 data contributing sites and from all 50 states are represented in this analysis. There are no date restrictions on this query.

There are two parallel sub-analyses, each with slightly different inclusion criteria. We provide a figure below that represents the sample size for each of these.

Analysis 1: Patients with a U09.9 diagnosis (versus those without U09.9)

Inclusion criteria for Analysis 1: All patients from the study cohort provided:

1. The patient has had at least one visit on or after October 2021 to ensure they had the opportunity to be diagnosed with U09.9).
2. The patient must come from one of the 25 sites with any patients diagnosed with U09.9 (relevant for the column labeled not U09.9).

Analysis 2: Patients with PASC (versus those without PASC) as defined by application of a machine-learning (ML) model that was trained on labels identifying patients who visit a long-covid clinic¹

Inclusion criteria for Analysis 2: All patients from the study cohort who are part of the machine-learning model output which includes the following restriction:

1. Patients must have had a follow-up visit at least 90 days after their COVID-19 index visit.
2. Note that this implicitly excludes patients who died within 45 days of their COVID-19 index visit.

Methods:

Each descriptive analysis was performed twice, once on all the patients meeting the inclusion criteria, and then again on only the subset of patients who had a COVID-19 hospitalization (see below figure). For all analyses, descriptive statistics are shown, including the number (N) and percentage of patients meeting criteria (%). Continuous data such as laboratory measurements are summarized by median and interquartile range (IQR).

Definitions:

COVID-19 hospitalization: A patient hospitalization +/- 14 days from first PCR/AG+ lab result or +/- 14 days from the first U07.1 diagnosis *that was documented during an inpatient or Emergency Department (ED) visit.*

COVID-19 ED visit: Emergency Department visit +/- 14 days from first PCR/AG+ lab result or if no lab result; or then +/- 14 days from the first U07.1 diagnosis *that was documented during an inpatient or emergency department (ED) visit.*

Inclusion Criteria and Cohort Description

Race and ethnicity across exclusion criteria

	Positive PCR/AG/U07.1/MISC			Index date			ML sample			U09.9 Site			Visit after 10/2021		
White non-Hispanic	2,225,348	58.4%		2,224,253	58.4%		704,546	62.2%		670,215	60.1%		429,374	65.2%	
Black non-Hispanic	480,306	12.6%		479,963	12.6%		169,438	15.0%		155,566	14.0%		97,567	14.8%	
Hispanic or Latino	522,622	13.7%		522,383	13.7%		158,604	14.0%		145,064	13.0%		72,501	11.0%	
Missing	484,991	12.7%		484,837	12.7%		69,784	6.2%		105,628	9.5%		37,198	5.7%	
Asian non-Hispanic	78,631	2.1%		78,579	2.1%		26,803	2.4%		26,459	2.4%		15,980	2.4%	
Other non-Hispanic	21,173	0.6%		21,158	0.6%		3,836	0.3%		11,892	1.1%		5,491	0.8%	

Gender across exclusion criteria

	Positive PCR/AG/U07.1/MISC		Index date		ML sample		U09.9 Site		Visit after 10/2021			
Female	2066202	54%		2065167	54%		603117	54%		378530	58%	
Male	1724327	45%		1723471	45%		510331	46%		279220	42%	
Missing	22542	1%		22535	1%		1376	0%		361	0%	

Observations:

The populations studied are fairly similar across exclusion criteria. We see less missing race/ethnicity as we make exclusions (12% reduced to 6% for both ML and U09.9 samples), and an increased proportion of patients that are white non-Hispanic and Black non-Hispanic. For gender, both the ML sample and the restriction to patients with a visit on or after 10/2021 increases the proportion of patients that are female.

Analysis 1: U09.9**Overall Sample**

	No U09.9 N = 649196	U09.9 N = 5469
White non-Hispanic	422954 (65.15%)	3933 (71.91%)
Black non-Hispanic	96420 (14.85%)	684 (12.51%)
Asian non-Hispanic	15827 (2.44%)	87 (1.59%)
Hispanic or Latino	71720 (11.05%)	509 (9.31%)
Other Non-Hispanic	5438 (0.84%)	36 (0.66%)
Race unknown	36837 (5.67%)	220 (4.02%)
Female	373691 (57.56%)	3395 (62.08%)
Male	275145 (42.38%)	2073 (37.9%)
Age at COVID-19 dx (mean)	41.6	50.9
Age at COVID-19 dx (median (IQR))	41.0 (25.0-58.0)	52.0 (40.0-62.0)
U09.9 dx	0 (0.0%)	5469 (100.0%)
Long COVID clinic visit	524 (0.08%)	295 (5.39%)
SARS-CoV-2 PCR or AG positive	483650 (74.5%)	3439 (62.88%)
U07.1 dx	480813 (74.06%)	5171 (94.55%)
MIS-C dx	329 (0.05%)	33 (0.6%)
COVID-19 ED visit	92522 (14.25%)	1051 (19.22%)
COVID-19 hospitalization	83002 (12.79%)	1983 (36.26%)
Observation period pre-COVID (mean)	849	888
Observation period post-COVID (mean)	153	176
Observation period pre-COVID (median (IQR))	909.0 (386.0-1164.0)	1022.0 (520.0-1242.0)
Observation period post-COVID (median (IQR))	61.0 (0.0-309.0)	114.0 (52.0-299.0)

Observations:

A minority of patients with a long COVID clinic visit actually have a U09.9 code. Unsurprisingly 5% of patients with U09.9 had a long COVID visit (because only 4 sites have a long COVID clinic). The U09.9 group had a higher percentage of Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C). U09.9 patients are more white non-Hispanic than patients without U09.9. U09.9 patients are older (~10 years on average), less likely to have had a positive test in the contributing site's medical record, and more likely to have a U07.1 diagnosis code. They are three times as likely to have an inpatient hospital visit within 14 days of a qualifying lab or diagnosis: of the patients with U09.9, 36% were hospitalized compared to 12% of those without U09.9 diagnosis. Those with U09.9 have longer pre- and post-COVID observation periods than those without the diagnosis.

Hospitalized During Acute COVID-19 Sample

	No U09.9 N=83002	U09.9 N=1983
White non-Hispanic	47758 (57.54%)	1347 (67.93%)
Black on-Hispanic	19462 (23.45%)	303 (15.28%)
Asian non-Hispanic	1724 (2.08%)	34 (1.71%)
Hispanic or Latino	10553 (12.71%)	223 (11.25%)
Race unknown	2913 (3.51%)	65 (3.28%)
Female	44386 (53.48%)	1033 (52.09%)
Male	38597 (46.5%)	949 (47.86%)
Age at COVID-19 dx (mean)	51.4969	55.3797
Age at COVID-19 dx (median (IQR))	54.0 (35.0-68.0)	57.0 (45.0-66.0)
U09.9 dx	0 (0.0%)	1983 (100.0%)
Long COVID clinic visit	303 (0.37%)	92 (4.64%)
SARS-CoV-2 PCR or AG positive	65265 (78.63%)	1518 (76.55%)
U07.1 dx	77529 (93.41%)	1972 (99.45%)
MIS-C dx	217 (0.26%)	23 (1.16%)
COVID-19 ED visit	12002 (14.46%)	393 (19.82%)
COVID-19 Hospitalization length of stay (mean)	6.0	14.4
COVID-19 Hospitalization length of stay (median (IQR))	3.0 (1.0-6.0)	6.0 (2.0-16.0)
Invasive mechanical ventilation during COVID-19 hospitalization	4470 (5.39%)	384 (19.36%)
ECMO during COVID-19 hospitalization	242 (0.29%)	44 (2.22%)
COVID-19 regimen corticosteroids during COVID-19 hosp.	37336 (44.98%)	1381 (69.64%)
Remdesivir during COVID-19 hospitalization	23370 (28.16%)	940 (47.4%)
Acute kidney injury during COVID-19 hospitalization	11643 (14.03%)	458 (23.1%)
Sepsis during COVID-19 hospitalization	8958 (10.79%)	436 (21.99%)
Vasopressors during COVID-19 hospitalization	7934 (9.56%)	355 (17.9%)
Max ferritin during COVID-19 hospitalization (sub-cohort mean)	884.6	1139.9
Min ferritin during COVID-19 hospitalization (sub-cohort mean)	762.6	930.8
Max D-Dimer during COVID-19 hospitalization (sub-cohort mean)	5.4	28.3
Min D-Dimer during COVID-19 hospitalization (sub-cohort mean)	5.2	28.1
Observation period pre-COVID (sub-cohort mean)	799.6	840.7
Observation period post-COVID (sub-cohort mean)	206.1	182.0
Observation period pre-COVID (median (IQR))	868.0 (213.0-1139.0)	1009.0 (289.5-1237.0)
Observation period post-COVID (median (IQR))	146.0 (15.0-363.0)	114.0 (64.0-294.5)

Observations: The observations for the overall sample continue to apply to those that were hospitalized during acute COVID-19, except for age: the hospitalized sample is more similar in age (~3 years older for U09.9 versus ~10 years older in the overall sample), perhaps due to hospitalized patients overall being older. Individuals with U09.9 have a longer length of stay during acute COVID hospitalization, were more likely to be ventilated, and more likely to be treated with ECMO. Patients diagnosed with U09.9 were more likely to be treated with corticosteroids, vasopressors and Remdesivir. They are also more likely to suffer from acute kidney injury (AKI) or sepsis during acute phase hospitalization.

For each patient, we also collected their min and max ferritin and D-dimer labs during COVID-19 hospitalization and then calculated the average for each sub-cohort. Patients diagnosed with PASC (U09.9) have higher D-dimer and also have higher ferritin during their COVID-19 hospitalizations than those without documented U09.9. This suggests that the issues with clotting and immune dysregulation that have been observed in COVID-19 patients are most pronounced in patients who go on to develop post-acute sequelae.

Unlike for the overall sample, those with U09.9 have slightly shorter post-COVID observation period (median (IQR)).

Analysis 2: Computable Phenotype

Computable Phenotype Overall Sample

	Not PASC N = 1053669	PASC N = 79342
White non-Hispanic	650933 (61.78%)	53613 (67.57%)
Black non-Hispanic	157307 (14.93%)	12131 (15.29%)
Asian non-Hispanic	25253 (2.4%)	1550 (1.95%)
Hispanic or Latino	150452 (14.28%)	8152 (10.27%)
Other Non-Hispanic	3585 (0.34%)	251 (0.32%)
Race unknown	66139 (6.28%)	3645 (4.59%)
Female	622062 (59.04%)	52749 (66.48%)
Male	431313 (40.93%)	26579 (33.5%)
Age at COVID-19 dx (mean)	46.8095	59.427
Age at COVID-19 dx (median (IQR))	46.0 (31.0-60.0)	61.0 (52.0-68.0)
U09.9 dx	2709 (0.26%)	613 (0.77%)
Long COVID clinic visit	281 (0.03%)	430 (0.54%)
SARS-CoV-2 PCR or AG positive	896207 (85.06%)	65156 (82.12%)
U07.1 dx	668394 (63.43%)	57116 (71.99%)
MIS-C dx	175 (0.02%)	<20
Visit on or after October 1 2021	527582 (50.07%)	44912 (56.61%)
U09.9 dx site	371720 (35.28%)	25106 (31.64%)
COVID-19 ED visit	168411 (15.98%)	13164 (16.59%)
COVID-19 hospitalization	186913 (17.74%)	22016 (27.75%)
Observation period pre-COVID (mean)	839.44	1049.9469
Observation period post-COVID (mean)	206.4517	235.605
Observation period pre-COVID (median (IQR))	866.0 (474.0-1051.0)	955.0 (709.0-1085.0)
Observation period post-COVID (median (IQR))	185.0 (33.0-327.0)	245.0 (22.0-363.0)

Observations:

In this analysis, we are comparing patients with high or low likelihood of PASC based upon our previously described ML model that was trained on long COVID clinic visits. Those who are predicted to have a higher (>.75) likelihood of PASC are similar to the lower probability cohort with respect to SARS-CoV-2 positive test or U07.1 diagnosis. The high-likelihood PASC patients have longer follow-up and are more likely to have a visit after October 2021; they are similar with respect to experiencing an ED visit during acute COVID-19, but were more likely to be hospitalized during acute COVID-19; they are slightly more white non-Hispanic (6pp), more female (7pp) and older (approx. 15 years) than those with <.75 predicted probability (as we saw in the first analysis that used U09.9).

Computable Phenotype Hospitalized During Acute COVID Sample

	Not PASC N = 186913	PASC N = 22016
White non-Hispanic	98733 (52.82%)	12919 (58.68%)
Black non-Hispanic	41266 (22.08%)	4706 (21.38%)
Asian non-Hispanic	4983 (2.67%)	518 (2.35%)
Hispanic or Latino	31362 (16.78%)	2819 (12.8%)
Other Non-Hispanic	695 (0.37%)	89 (0.4%)
Race unknown	9874 (5.28%)	965 (4.38%)
Female	100529 (53.78%)	12353 (56.11%)
Male	86363 (46.2%)	9661 (43.88%)
Age at COVID-19 dx (mean)	55.8226	63.0595
Age at COVID-19 dx (median (IQR))	57.0 (40.0-71.0)	64.0 (56.0-72.0)
U09.9 dx	1161 (0.62%)	250 (1.14%)
Long COVID clinic visit	137 (0.07%)	281 (1.28%)
SARS-CoV-2 PCR or AG positive	158265 (84.67%)	19022 (86.4%)
U07.1 dx	163014 (87.21%)	19425 (88.23%)
MIS-C dx	122 (0.07%)	<20
Visit on or after October 1 2021	93136 (49.83%)	11205 (50.89%)
U09.9 dx site	59616 (31.9%)	6136 (27.87%)
COVID-19 ED visit	29418 (15.74%)	3245 (14.74%)
COVID-19 Hospitalization length of stay (mean)	7.5455	10.6572
COVID-19 Hospitalization length of stay (median (IQR))	4.0 (1.0-7.0)	5.0 (2.0-10.0)
Invasive mechanical ventilation during COVID-19 hospitalization	9526 (5.1%)	1696 (7.7%)
ECMO during COVID-19 hospitalization	616 (0.33%)	145 (0.66%)
COVID-19 regimen corticosteroids during COVID-19 hospitalization	73892 (39.53%)	9831 (44.65%)
Remdesivir during COVID-19 hospitalization	29524 (15.8%)	4288 (19.48%)
Acute kidney injury during COVID-19 hospitalization	26558 (14.21%)	4095 (18.6%)
Sepsis during COVID-19 hospitalization	21796 (11.66%)	3197 (14.52%)
Vasopressors during COVID-19 hospitalization	18141 (9.71%)	2316 (10.52%)
Max ferritin during COVID-19 hospitalization (sub-cohort mean)	915.0907	993.0581
Min ferritin during COVID-19 hospitalization (sub-cohort mean)	801.3134	869.2873
Max D-Dimer during COVID-19 hospitalization (sub-cohort mean)	4.5877	6.8471
Min D-Dimer during COVID-19 hospitalization (sub-cohort mean)	4.3199	6.3996
Observation period pre-COVID (mean)	904.7274	1102.7116
Observation period post-COVID (mean)	258.976	232.3508
Observation period pre-COVID (median (IQR))	834.0 (371.0-1056.0)	919.0 (609.0-1086.0)
Observation period post-COVID (median (IQR))	235.0 (94.0-359.0)	221.0 (26.0-363.0)

Observations:

The PASC and non-PASC patients from the hospitalized sample are more similar along diagnoses, ED visits, and demographics than in the overall population. Those defined as PASC by the training model (i.e., predicted probability >.75) had a longer length of stay, more likely to have IMV, more likely to receive corticosteroids, Remdesivir and vasopressors during COVID-19 hospitalization but these differences are less pronounced than the U09.9 analysis; they are more likely to have AKI and sepsis during COVID-19 hospitalization. The follow up

periods for the hospitalized patients is more similar than the overall sample likely reflecting that hospitalized patients have more interactions with the health system. Approximately 30% of patients are recorded in a site using U09.9 and about 50% of patients had a visit on or after October 2021 to be eligible for the diagnosis.

Discussion

When considering demographics and features describing the COVID-19 index visit, patients identified via U09.9 see large differences between those with and without the diagnosis, however, we do not see as stark of differences among patients identified with the ML model definition of PASC, which was trained based on long COVID clinic utilization. For example, D-dimer and ferritin are fairly similar for the ML sample but show stark differences for U09.9.

Limitations and Future work:

- The major limitation of using the ML model continues to be the modest size of the training set defining the model of PASC. Training labels (long-covid clinic usage) come from four of the 69 sites considered in this analysis. As such, there are considerable heterogeneity issues between sites that will require further attention as more data become available. Future work will consider other training labels such as the emerging U09.9 diagnosis code.
- Not all medical events recorded at the site are sent to N3C due to local data mapping and extraction practices. Thus, our reported counts of drugs and procedures are lower than one would expect in patients hospitalized for COVID-19.
- These data represent a sample-of-convenience and are not meant to fully represent population dynamics within the US.